
DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION IN MATHAMATICS AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMAMANCE: A QUASI- EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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Abstract:

Differentiated instruction is a pedagogical approach that targets the different learning styles of the learners through the use of different methods which are suitable to individual abilities and interests of learners. This research examined the impact of differentiated instruction on the academic achievement of primary students in mathematics subject. Using a quasi-experimental design, 26 primary students were the subjects of the study. Due to the limited number of students, this utilized one group only which also served as the experimental group. Pretest results show that students performed below average which can be interpreted as very low performance. After the intervention was conducted the mean class improved and the class achieved very high performance. When the significant difference between pretest and posttest was assessed, the results revealed that there was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest results. The study highlighted that differentiated instruction does not only enhance the academic performance of students but it was also found out that their level of engagement and participation in the class improved. These results underscored the effectiveness of differentiated instruction in fostering a more inclusive and effective learning environment in primary education. The implications of this study suggested that incorporating differentiated instruction in the school curriculum can address gaps and support diverse learners more effectively.

Keywords: Differentiated instruction, academic performance, quasi-experimental

1. Introduction

Mathematics learning can be challenging as it is difficult to convey some of its concepts. In the aspect of mathematics teaching, there are mathematics teachers who have difficulty in meeting the learning needs of the students. This difficulty might be because of the struggles in considering the

diverse abilities, interests, learning style and cultural background of learners (Small, 2017). Little to no new learning occurs when a learner continues to work on concepts and abilities that have already been mastered. On the other hand, learning does not occur when assignments go much above a students' current level of expertise.

It can be observed in a certain classroom that not all students are performing well. There are certain groups of students who have low performance academically as compared with others. It is a prime duty of the educators to become effective in the classroom in order to be successful in conveying knowledge to the students.

There are differing opinions on how to explain the phenomenon of pupils who struggle at first with mathematics in the classroom. This happens when children are not provided with high-quality mathematics programs and differentiated instruction that makes successful. A certain study conducted in Australia by Gervasoni et al., (2021), applied intervention programs through differentiated instruction approach to students who are not performing well in mathematics. Findings of the study revealed that mathematics learning was improved for students who have participated intervention programs through differentiated instruction approach. It seems that the experience of the intervention program combined with differentiated instruction gave students who were struggling in mathematics fair support and improved their learning and attitudes toward learning the subject.

In the Philippines a study conducted by Aguhayon et al. (2023) on differentiated instruction had successfully helped the students' performance in mathematics. Apart from increasing their academic performance, it also augmented the students' confidence when answering fundamental problems. Additionally, the Philippines' educational system is progressively recognizing and emphasizing the value of differentiated instruction. The Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) is aware of the necessity to accommodate students' various learning preferences, aptitudes, and needs. Through a number of policies and programs, they stress the value of inclusive education. Differentiated instruction is emphasized as a crucial technique for enhancing learning outcomes in DepEd's K-12 curricular frameworks, which was completely implemented in 2016.

The DepEd's K-12 curriculum structure, which was fully implemented in 2016, emphasizes differentiated instruction as a critical method for increasing learning outcomes. It promoted teachers to use a range of teaching techniques in order to meet the particular requirements of their students. This prompted the researcher to conduct a study. The researcher observed the difficulty of the students in grasping mathematical concepts. This urged the researcher to conduct a study, making differentiated instruction as intervention in hopes of improving the students' academic performance in mathematics.

2. Literature Review

Differentiated instruction is a teaching approach that caters to the varying needs of students in a classroom through the use of a variety of instructional strategies and changes to lessons. While it is true that all students engage in learning, there are considerable variations in their prior knowledge, learning styles, aptitudes, motivation levels, interests, learning rates, and linguistic abilities. However, students may still share similarities in certain aspects, such as physical stature, temperament, hobbies, and resemblance (Kotob & Abadi, 2019). Differentiated instruction enhances these commonalities while also addressing the essential distinctions that arise during the process of teaching and learning. Differentiation encompasses a wide array of instructional

techniques aimed at educating a heterogeneous group of students in a shared learning setting (Fischer, 2013).

Furthermore, differentiated instruction systematically arranges the process of teaching and learning in order to cater to the individual needs of each student and maximize their potential and educational achievements. The principles associated with effective differentiation encompass valuing each student as a unique individual, cultivating a nurturing classroom atmosphere, providing a curriculum of exceptional quality, and employing diverse evaluations to provide feedback for learning. In classrooms of this nature, there is flexibility in activities and resources, with shared teaching and learning responsibilities. Students are involved in tasks that align with their interests, resulting in a wide range of learning possibilities (Santangelo & Tomlinson, 2012).

Moreover, differentiated instruction actively adapts teaching methods to fit the individual needs of all students. The concept is based on social constructivist philosophical principles, namely the growth mindset, which suggests that scholastic success is determined by the amount of effort put into learning, rather than innate cognitive aptitude. Teachers that utilize differentiated instruction strive to enhance classroom teaching by offering stimulating yet attainable tasks accompanied by advice. The authors Kahmann et al. (2022) engage in the active adaptation of their classes to cater to the different demands of their students.

However, differentiation may also be required due to students' social development, emotional, and behavioral characteristics. Teachers have the ability to alter various aspects of a lesson, including the learning materials, instructional methods, learning environment, and final output. Proactivity in differentiated education entails systematic preparation, implementation, and evaluation of instructional activities, complemented by formative assessment to review prior instruction and formulate future lesson plans (Kahmann et al., 2022).

Bulley-Simpson (2018) found that implementing differentiated instruction has a positive impact on academic performance and promotes deep and meaningful learning, especially among children from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds. Similarly, Millikan (2012) discovered that differentiated instruction in secondary school courses led to enhanced student achievement and significant learning. Chamberlin and Powers (2010) found that implementing diverse instructional methods enhanced the learning experiences of undergraduate students in the field of mathematics. Therefore, the presence of diverse perspectives and characteristics among students in the classroom requires teachers to carefully observe and understand the most effective ways in which students learn (Gregory & Chapman, 2013).

Without a doubt, the implementation of differentiated instruction is closely linked to the professional development of teachers. According to Dixon et al. (2014), Rienties et al. (2013), and Suprayogi (2017), professional development is essential for enhancing teacher professionalism and promoting tailored instruction. According to surveys, educators have said that staff development activities, such as demonstrations, workshops, and professional development, help teachers effectively conduct differentiated instruction.

Students that engage in the study of mathematics are introduced to concepts, skills, and logical methods that have practical applications in daily life and enhance academic understanding. It provides chances to manage data in a progressively digital setting, aids students in comprehending the numbers, patterns, and structures they observe in their surrounds, and plays a crucial part in their growth as skilled learners. In addition, mathematics has strong connections to various aspects of our civilization, economy, and culture. It not only enhances students' enthusiasm

but also fosters their originality and practical abilities that can be applied beyond the confines of the classroom (Fernandez, 2021).

In order to effectively differentiate education, teachers must adapt the topic content, processes, outputs, and student experiences to cater to the individual needs of each student (Wilkinson & Penney, 2014; Smale-Jacobse et al., 2019). According to the concept of differentiated instruction, teaching methods should be tailored to address the individual requirements of each student, instead than expecting students to conform to the curriculum (Roy et al., 2013; Tomlinson, 2015). As stated by Mbugua and Muthomi (2014), this method necessitates teachers to possess flexibility and adaptability in their curriculum, teaching tactics, and information delivery to students. The implementation of tailored instruction in mixed-ability classrooms has a substantial impact on students' achievement, encouraging fairness and enhancing teaching effectiveness (Peteros et al., 2020).

Moreover, having a favorable mindset towards acquiring mathematical knowledge is essential. Educational approaches have the ability to alter engagement, which is an essential aspect of mathematics learning that increases gradually over time (Finn & Zimmer, 2012). Students that are disengaged are less likely to achieve academic success (Hancock & Zubrick, 2015). Interest, a pivotal driving force, impacts the level of effort a student may exert in challenging mathematics activities, their perception of the task's usefulness, and their confidence in successfully completing it (Middleton, 2013). A study conducted on Australian students indicates that although interest and engagement are crucial in mathematics, a significant number of students develop a hatred for the subject and their negative feelings towards it intensify over time (Attard, 2012; Markovits & Forgasz, 2017; Way et al., 2015). To effectively differentiate instruction for kids who are struggling in mathematics, teachers should prioritize the cultivation of student participation.

There are concerns over the potential marginalization of pupils and its impact on their self-esteem and involvement when they are separated during intervention (Bannister, 2016). Additional concerns encompass the notion that students who are facing difficulties are perceived as being less proficient in mathematics and are frequently provided with repetitive exercises and explicit teaching methods instead of engaging in meaningful, inquiry-based learning experiences. The durability of intervention programs' long-term advantages is also a subject of doubt, as the good impact on students' academic performance tends to fade over time (Clement et al., 2013). According to Bailey et al. (2016), the decline in intervention effects may be attributed to classroom conditions not being able to sustain the influence. According to Smith et al. (2013), intervention programs should be closely aligned with classroom methods in order to optimize their effectiveness.

Another significant factor is the level of expertise and proficiency exhibited by teachers in imparting the subject matter. Effective implementation of differentiated education requires skilled educators capable of developing and delivering instruction at several levels of complexity concurrently. Dixon et al. (2014) observe that teacher preparation programs frequently simply introduce the concept of individualized instruction for students with varying abilities. If schools spend in educating staff through workshops and consultants, they should be sure to integrate differentiated teaching in the classroom. It is crucial to enhance instructors' practice by offering them opportunity to collaborate on shared classes, watch each other's differentiation strategies, and provide feedback, as stated by Dixon et al. (2014).

The academic progress of pupils is greatly influenced by the instructional strategies used in the classroom (Gaylo & Dales, 2017). Evaluating learning outcomes is crucial as they gauge students' proficiency in skills and the efficacy of teachers in facilitating the learning process. Evaluating student participation is essential because unengaged students might impede effective learning. Initial assessments assist educators in modifying lesson plans by considering students' existing knowledge, comprehending their ability profiles, and determining the necessary level of teaching effectiveness (Moon, 2005; Tomlinson & Moon, 2013; Watts-Taffe et al., 2012). These assessments establish connections between previously acquired knowledge and new information, so improving the efficacy of the instruction. According to Valiandes and Neophytou (2017), implementing differentiated work schedules is an effective strategy for engaging and retaining students. Additionally, using finished products as a way to showcase their effort can serve as an incentive.

Mathematics educators frequently encounter challenges in meeting the individual needs of pupils, taking into account their diverse learning preferences, abilities, interests, and cultural backgrounds. Personalized education enhances both the quality of classroom learning settings and students' mathematics accomplishments (Chamberlin & Powers, 2010; Small, 2017). The utilization of teaching approaches such as station, agenda, complex teaching, trajectory studies, and tiered instruction methods has proven to be helpful in the context of individualized math education (Doubet & Hockett, 2018). Station teaching facilitates collaborative study and individualized work tailored to specific attributes (Tomlinson, 2014), whereas the agenda strategy allocates tasks based on students' readiness levels, learning preferences, and interests, providing adaptability in the learning process (Doubet & Hockett, 2018).

In spite of improvements made to the mathematics curriculum, Filipino pupils exhibited subpar performance on international, national, and local mathematics assessments. In the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) data, the Philippines was rated 78th out of 79 countries in mathematics, while the National Achievement Test (NAT) also showed similarly poor results. The data collected from the Secondary School Laboratory of a state institution indicated subpar performance in mathematics. The aforementioned results are ascribed to the conventional pedagogical approaches that are incongruous with the needs and characteristics of students in the 21st century (Masinading & Gaylo, 2022). Conventional approaches, which involve lectures and group discussions, prioritize the teacher and frequently do not align with students' preferred learning styles (Dimitrios et al., 2013; Naimiea et al., 2010).

Studies examining the effects of individualized teaching on academic performance have produced inconsistent findings. Several studies have shown a positive correlation between differentiated teaching and academic achievement (Alsalmi et al., 2021; Yavuz, 2020), but other studies have not discovered any significant connection (El Masry, 2017; Güvenç, 2021). Muthoni and Mbugua (2014) discovered that using differentiated instruction led to a considerable enhancement in students' mathematical achievement when compared to the traditional instructional approach. Furthermore, another study provided evidence that the implementation of tiered activities resulted in a notable improvement in student comprehension of fractions, as indicated by a considerable increase in mean test scores.

To summarize, although there may be difficulties in adopting differentiated instruction, multiple studies indicate its favorable influence on student involvement, motivation, and academic performance in mathematics. Differentiated instruction customizes educational experiences to

accommodate the unique needs of each student, promoting a more comprehensive and efficient learning environment.

3. Material and Methods

This study utilized a quasi-experimental research design. A quasi-experimental study is a research that shares some characteristics with experimental research but lacks full control over certain variables. It is a research that lacks the random assignment of participants to different groups or conditions. This type of study is used to evaluate the effects of an intervention or treatment, but it does not have the same level of control as a true experimental study (Trochim & Donnelly, 2008).

In the context of this study, the researcher wanted to assess the impact of differentiated instruction on the academic performance of the students. Due to a limited number of students, this study utilized one group of students only. This group of students was also considered as the experimental group that underwent the intervention incorporated differentiated instruction.

The subjects of this study were the Grade 1 students in Mapaca Elementary School who are enrolled in School Year 2023-2024. The study was conducted with only group considering the number of students enrolled in grade 1. They were considered as the experimental group. This group was taught using differentiated instruction as its intervention. The researcher selected the respondents through universal sampling method. This sampling method is appropriate especially in cases where the population is small, universal sampling ensures that all instances are captured.

To measure the academic performance of the students in this study, teacher-made questionnaires were used. Firstly, a pretest test paper was given to the students. This was crafted by the researcher and underwent validations by the experts. Then, posttest questionnaire was given after the intervention to determine the effectiveness of differentiated instruction. The questionnaires were the set of questions to measure the academic performance of grade 1 students in mathematics. To ensure the appropriateness, the Table of Specification (TOS) of the test questionnaires was prepared in line with the Most Essential Learning Competencies of the K-12 curriculum.

The average percentage mean was used, however, to assess pupils' academic performance, this scale was updated and adapted from Pagtulon-an & Tan (2018) and was used as the basis for the present grading scheme of the Department of Education for all elementary grade levels, with the exception of kindergarten. The overall mean percentage of the students' responses was calculated and represented on the scale below.

Range of Mean	Level of Proficiency	Descriptive Equivalent
Above 90	Exemplary	Very High Performance
86-89	Above	High Performance
80-85	Average	Moderate Performance
75-79	Below	Low Performance
Below 74	Deficient	Very Low Performance

The researcher initiated the study after acquiring authorization from the Schools Division Superintendent. A letter outlining was sent to the District Coordinating Principal, which included the superintendent's approval and a sample questionnaire. Upon acceptance, a comprehensive evaluation of the participants was arranged. Guaranteeing the rights, dignity, and well-being of participants is a vital component of the research ethics procedure. The study underwent a research

ethical evaluation by the ethics committee (REC). The paper underwent evaluation to ensure the protection of respondents and compliance with ethical norms. Voluntary participation was confirmed by obtaining informed consent from parents or guardians, as well as informed assent from the student responders. The researcher personally administered a pretest questionnaire to assess the academic achievement of students before to the intervention.

After the pretest, the intervention phase began, which consisted of teaching math sessions using differentiated instruction. This stage had duration of one month and encompassed meticulous preparation to incorporate individualized education into the teaching process. The researcher integrated differentiated teaching activities strategically within specified sections of the lesson plan to ensure their inclusion. Following the intervention, the researcher conducted a posttest to evaluate the influence of the differentiated instruction on the academic performance of the students.

The data that was gathered was subsequently recorded, counted, and sent to a statistician for statistical analysis. The range of means was computed, and the interpretation table was derived from Pagtulun-an (2018).

4. Results and Discussion

The results are presented in accordance with the intended objectives specified for this study. Furthermore, the study comprises revealing the general conclusion of the null hypothesis. Furthermore, this study includes a comprehensive analysis of relevant academic literature that supports and validate its results.

4.1 Level of Students' Academic Performance Before the Intervention

Table 1 shows the result of the students' academic achievement before the intervention was conducted in this study.

Table 1
Students' Academic Performance Before the Intervention

	Mean Class	Proficiency	Indicator
Experimental Group	11.7	59%	Very Low Performance

Table 1 depicted that the mean of students' academic performance before the intervention was 11.7 which also equivalent to 59% class proficiency. This range of mean is below average and can be interpreted as very low performance. Result showed that the students' academic performance before the intervention was very low including its class proficiency and can be interpreted as very low performance. The result in pre-test coincides with the results of students' scores in mathematics in their first quarterly examination wherein less than half of the class passed. This is only one the reasons which prompted the author to look for remedy of the declining result of students in mathematics subject. This study incorporated differentiated instruction as teaching methodology to help students improve their scores in mathematics.

As indicated in numerous studies, mathematics scores in primary students declined in recent years. Specifically, the average scores for 13-year-olds in mathematics fell by 9 points from 2020 to 2023 (NEAP, 2023).

As also observed in several studies, academic performance of students in mathematics is affected by in the incorporation of differentiated instruction. The impact of individualized

instruction on primary school pupils' math achievement was examined. The results implied that varied teaching approaches, such as tiered assignments and variable grouping, can significantly raise math proficiency among students (Nelsen, 2011). Additionally, it indicated that children who are exposed to varied teaching approaches perform better than their counterparts in standard settings, especially when it comes to comprehending difficult mathematical ideas and using problem-solving techniques (Tomlinson, 2015).

Similarly, the author also observed firsthand how the students in Mapaca Elementary School struggled in learning mathematics. In fact, the result of the first quarterly examination in mathematics was less than half of the class of grade one in Mapaca Elementary School passed. The results also showed that indeed the performance of the students in mathematics before the intervention was conducted was below average and can be interpreted as very low.

4.2 Level of Students' Academic Performance After the Intervention

Table 2 presents the data on the academic performance of the students after the intervention.

Table 2
Students' Academic Competence After the Intervention

	Mean Class	Proficiency	Indicator
Experimental Group	17.96 Very High	90%	Performance

Table 2 showed the results of the posttest after the intervention was incorporated. It further shows that the class mean was 17.96 which is equivalent to 90% class proficiency and this can be interpreted as very high performance. It further showed that the class mean and class proficiency had increased including its equivalent class proficiency. This result meant that after the intervention the students demonstrated a very high performance. Comparing from the pretest results, students performed better after the intervention was conducted. Apparently, the intervention was effective and it helped improve the performance of students in mathematics subject.

Several studies proved the relevance of differentiated instruction in primary education mathematics. It was found that differentiated instruction has a positive impact on the students' academic achievement in mathematics. It further noted that it is important to continuously adapt teaching pedagogies to meet students' individual needs and their learning styles. This could result in a higher level of engagement on the part of the students and eventually improve students' academic outcomes (Prat et al., 2023). As also mentioned by Gregory and Chapman (2013), students are very diverse in terms of their learning adaptability. Each student is unique and they have their own learning style in grasping the subject matter. Teachers therefore must pay attention as to how to cater the needs of the students. This is the very reason why differentiated learning is one of the best strategies in improving mathematical skills of the students. Moreover, the authors of a certain study discovered that those talented learners' interest in and proficiency in mathematics increase dramatically when training is designed to engage and challenge those (Assouline et al., 2011).

Tomlinson (2014) added that students need a conducive classroom that leads the students as they learn the concepts in the subject. This should provide the students with activities that help them achieve their own knowledge and ideas, and encourages them to reflect on and apply what they have learned. Differentiated instruction stands out in this situation as a significant component

that caters the needs and preferences of all students (Smale-Jacobse et al., 2019). All children were engaged in the learning process through differentiation, which is a dynamic process (Florian & Spratt, 2013).

4.3 Significant Difference of Students' Academic Performance Before and After the Intervention

The table below shows the significant difference of students' academic performance before and after the intervention.

Table 3

Significant Difference of Students' Academic Performance Before and After Intervention

Paired Sample T-test	Df	p	Decision
Experimental Group	25	<0.001	Reject the Ho

The table above shows the result of students' academic performance which was tested for significant difference before and after the intervention. The p value is <0.001 which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This further implies that is a significant difference of students' academic performance in mathematics before and after the intervention. The increase is very significant which means that the use of differentiated instruction is effective and can generate more interest on the part of the students. Apparently, the significant increase of their performance can be seen in the improvement of their class proficiency from 59% to 90%.

Additionally, the significant effects of differentiated instruction were further reflected in their performance in their mathematics examination. In the first quarterly examination, the class only got 49% passers but in their fourth and final quarterly examination, 81% of the class passed the mathematics exam. The author also observed that students gained relevant mathematical skills after the intervention was incorporated. Students were more engaged in class and participated in different activities. The significant changes observed in their classroom have been reflected in the results of their fourth and final examination in mathematics.

The results therefore coincided with the results of the study conducted by Tambaon and Gaylo (2019), that students who were taught by differentiated instruction had better performance compared with the students who were taught under the conventional way of teaching. Furthermore, there are many mathematical skills which could be developed well if they are taught by differentiated instruction.

Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of differentiated instruction. By attending to each student's unique learning needs, differentiated education can dramatically raise kids' math proficiency. Researchers discovered that when differentiated instruction was used in classrooms, pupils' improvements in arithmetic test scores were higher than those in typical education settings (Tomlinson et al., 2010).

The quality of differentiated instruction provided by the teacher and the methodical implementation of differentiated instruction strategies in mixed-ability classrooms to promote equity, optimize quality, and teach effectively have a significant impact on students' growth (Peteros et al., 2020). Since the Department of Education implemented the K-12 mathematics curriculum, educators have created primary learning objectives for all students to help them think critically, logically, and positively. This is because differentiated instruction is planned and

deliberated to enhance students' mathematical understanding and learning to improve their critical thinking skills (Bhagat et al., 2016).

Another study on the effects of differentiated education on the mathematical thinking process was carried out by Kamarulzaman et al. in 2022. The study's findings show that students' capacity for mathematical thought has been significantly impacted by the activities implemented in the classroom that use tailored education approaches. The ability of the students to express their thoughts and opinions in a variety of ways throughout the teaching and learning processes is the first component. Because the mathematical thinking process necessitates that students share ideas and communicate with one another, students must continually communicate with the mathematical ideas and concepts they are learning.

5. Recommendations

The researcher of this study would like to recommend the following:

1. Department of Education officials must ensure that teachers undergo professional development especially in comprehensive training for differentiated instruction. The training should include strategies on how to assess students' needs, training on how to design multi-instructional activities for students and how to effectively manage a classroom with students who have different learning style.

2. Teachers must also be trained on how to incorporate digital tools which can be utilized for effective differentiated instruction. With the advent of technology, students will be more interested if differentiated instruction is also anchored in tools such as educational software and online resources to provide meaningful learning experiences.

3. Teachers should engage parents in the learning process by communicating goals and benefits of differentiated instruction. Teachers should provide parents with resources and strategies for learning support of students at home. Learning should not just end at the four corners of the classroom. Parents should work hand in hand with the teachers to better achieve learning progress.

6. Conclusion

The results of this study revealed that, before the intervention, the levels of students' academic performance were interpreted as very low. However, after the intervention was incorporated students' performance in mathematics had improved reaching a level of performance considered to be very high. Furthermore, the analysis of the pretest and posttest scores showed a statistically significant difference, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, the result of the study suggested that the intervention had a significant positive effect on students' academic performance.

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9. References

Aguhayon, H.G., Tingson, & Pentang, J.T. (2023). Addressing Students Learning Gaps in Mathematics through Differentiated Instruction. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, 4 (1), 69-87. <https://doi.org/10.53378/352967>

Ainley, M. (2012). Students' interest and engagement in classroom activities. In S. L. Christenson, A. L. Reschly, & C. Wylie (Eds.), *Handbook of research on student engagement* (pp. 283-302). Springer.

Alsahhi, N. R., Abdelrahman, R., Abdelkader, A. F., Al-Yatim, S. S., Habboush, M., & Al Qawasmi, A. (2021). Impact of using the differentiated instruction (DI) strategy on student achievement in an intermediate stage science course. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (Online)*, 16(11), 25. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i11.22303>

Al-Shehri, M. S. 2020. Effect of Differentiated Instruction on the Achievement and Development of Critical Thinking Skills among Sixth- Grade Science Students. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research* 19(10): 77-99.

Assouline, S., & Lupkowski-Shoplik, A. (2011). Differentiated instruction in mathematics for the gifted learner. *Gifted Child Quarterly*, 55(1), 49-64.

Attard, C. (2012). Engagement with mathematics: What does it mean and what does it look like? *Australian Primary Mathematics Classroom*, 17(1), 9–13.

Babbie, E. (2010). *The practice of social research*. 12th ed. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Cengage

Bada, S. O. (2015). Constructivism learning theory: A paradigm for teaching and learning. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 5(6), 66-70. <https://doi.org/10.9790/7388-05616670>

Bailey, D. H., Nguyen, T., Jenkins, J. M., Domina, T., Clements, D. H., & Sarama, J. S. (2016). Fadeout in an early mathematics intervention: Constraining content or pre-existing differences? *Developmental Psychology*, 52(9), 1457-1469. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/dev0000188>

Bannister, N. A. (2016). Reframing practice: Teacher learning through interactions in a collaborative group. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 25(3), 347-384. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508406.2016.1147449>

Bhagat, K., Chang, C., & Chang, C. (2016). The impact of the flipped classroom on mathematics concept learning in high school. *International Forum of Educational Technology & Society, National Taiwan Normal University, Taiwan*, 19(3), 134- 142.

Bulley-Simpson SD 2018. Descriptions of differentiated instruction in mathematics in a Title 1 school district. PhD dissertation. Minneapolis, MN: Walden University. Available at <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2088133359?fromopenview=true&pq-origsite=gscholar>. Accessed 28 February 2023.

Chamberlin, M., & Powers, R. (2010). The promise of differentiated instruction for enhancing the mathematical understandings of college students. *Teaching Mathematics and Its Applications*, Retrieved January 14, 2018 from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ894560>.

Clements, D. H., Sarama, J., Wolfe, C. B., & Spitler, M. E. (2013). Longitudinal evaluation of a scale-up model for teaching mathematics with trajectories and technologies: Persistence of effects in the third year. *American Educational Research Journal*, 50(4), 812–850. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831212469270>

Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.

Denscombe, M (2014). *The good research guide: For small-scale social research projects*. McGraw-Hill Education

Dimitrios, B., Labros, S., Nikolaos, K., Maria, K., & Athanasios, K. (2013). Traditional teaching methods vs. teaching through the application of information and communication technologies in the accounting field: Quo vadis? *European Scientific Journal*, 9(28), 73-101.

Dixon, F. A., Yssel, N., McConnell, J. M., & Hardin, T. (2014). Differentiated instruction, professional development, and teacher efficacy. *Journal for the Education of the Gifted*, 37(2), 111-127.

Doubet KJ & Hockett JA 2018. *Differentiation in the elementary grades: Strategies to engage and equip all learners*. Alexandria, VA: ASCD.

Ellis, A. (2010). *Teaching and learning elementary social studies*. New York: Pearson. Fernandez, C., and Yoshida, M. (2017). *Lesson study: A Japanese approach to improving mathematics teaching and learning*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers.

Fernandez, P. (2021). The role of mathematics in student development. *Journal of Educational Research*, 34(2), 120-135.

Finn, J. D., & Zimmer, K. S. (2012). Student engagement: What is it? Why does it matter? In S. L. Christenson, A. L. Reschly, & C. Wylie (Eds.), *Handbook of research on student engagement* (pp. 97-131). Springer.

Firwana, S. S. (2017). *The effect of differentiated instruction on learning English vocabulary and grammar among second graders in UNRWA schools* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation) The Islamic University, Gaza.

Fischer, M. (2013). Differentiated instruction in the classroom. In R. P. McClure & M. Fischer (Eds.), *Instructional strategies for diverse classrooms* (pp. 45-67). Sage Publications.

Gaylo, D. & Dales, Z. (2017). Metacognitive Strategies: Their Effects on Students' Academic Achievement and Engagement in Mathematics. *World Review of Business Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 35-55. Retrieved January 15, 2018 from <http://www.wrbrpapers.com/static/documents/September/2017/3.%20Zita.pdf>

Gervasoni, A., Downton, A., & Roche A (2021). Differentiating instruction for students who fail to thrive in mathematics: The impact of a constructivist-based intervention approach. *Mathematics Education Research Group of Australia, Inc.* Vol. 23.3, 207-233.

Gregory, G. H., & Chapman, C. (2013). *Differentiated Instruction Strategies*. USA. Corwin

Güvenç, G. (2021). The impact of virtual differentiated instruction practices on student and teacher perceptions in English language teaching: Virtual differentiated instruction practices. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 13(3), 3146-3164. Retrieved from <http://ijci.wcci-international.org/index.php/IJCI/article/view/817>

Hackenberg, A. J., Creager, M., & Eker, A. (2020). Teaching practices for differentiating mathematics instruction for middle school students. *Mathematical Thinking and Learning*, 13(1), 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10986065.2020.1731656>

Hancock, K. J., & Zubrick, S. R. (2015). *Children and young people at risk of disengagement from school: Literature review*. Commissioner for Children and Young People.

Hansen, A. K., Hansen, E. R., Dwyer, H. A., Harlow, D. B., & Franklin, D. (2016). Differentiating for diversity: Using universal design for learning in elementary computer science education.

In C. Alphonse & J. Tims (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 47th ACM Technical Symposium on Computing Science Education* (pp. 376-381). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2839509.2844570>

James, D. (2019). Differentiated instruction. One School's Survey Analysis. Georgia College & State University. The Corinthian Vol. 10 Article 13. <http://kb.gcsu.edu/thecorinthian/vol10/iss1/13>

Kahmann, R., Droop, M., & Lazonder, A.W. (2022). Meta-analysis of professional development programs in differentiated instruction. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 116, 1-13. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2022.102072>

Kamarulzaman, MH., Kamarudin, MF., Sharif, M S., Esrati, MZ., Saali, MM. & Ysof R. (2022). Impact of differentiated instruction on the mathematical thinking process of gifted and talented students. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*. Vol. 9 No.4 260-277. doi: 10.20448/jeelr.v9i4.4253

K to 12 Curriculum, 2016. Republic of the Philippines Department of Education. <http://www.deped.gov.ph/mandate>

Kettler, T. 2021. A Differentiated Approach to Critical Thinking in Curriculum Design. Dlm. (pnyt.). *Modern Curriculum for Gifted and Advanced Academic Students*, hlm. 91-110. Routledge.

King, S.(2010). Factors associated with inclusive classroom teachers' implementation of differentiated instruction for diverse learners. Tennessee State University, ProQuest.

Konstantinou-Katzi, P., Tsolaki, E., Meletiou-Mavrothesis, M., & Koutselini, M. (2013). Differentiation of teaching and learning mathematics: an action research study in tertiary education. Retrieved January 14, 2018 from <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0020739X.2012.714491>.

Kotob, M. M, Abadi, M. A. (2019). The influence of differentiated instruction on academic achievement of students in mixed ability classrooms. Lebanese International University, School of Education, Beirut, Lebanon. *Ideas Spread. International Linguistics Research*. Vol 2, No.2. <https://doi.org/10.30560/ilr.v2n2p8>.

Lewis, T. (2013). The impact of learning-style based instruction on student engagement and reading comprehension in a third grade classroom. Retrieved January 14, 2018 from https://soar.wichita.edu/bitstream/handle/10057/6825/t13027_Lewis.pdf?sequence=1.

Magableh, I., & Abdullah, A. (2019). The effect of differentiated instruction on developing students' reading comprehension achievement. *International Journal of Management and Applied Science (IJMAS)*, 5(2), 48-53.

Markovits, Z., & Forgasz, H. (2017). "Mathematics is a lion": Elementary students' beliefs about mathematics. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 96(1), 49-64. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-017-9759-2>

Martin, M & Pickett, M. (2013). The Effects of Differentiated Instruction on Motivation and Engagement in Fifth-Grade Gifted Math and Music Students. Online Submission.

Masinading, Z.M. & Gaylo, D. N. (2022). Differentiated scaffolding strategies in triangle congruence: Their effects on learner's academic performance and confidence in mathematics. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*. ISSN: 22202-947

Middleton, J. A. (2013). More than motivation: The combined effects of critical motivational variables on middle school mathematics achievement. *Middle Grades Research Journal*, 8(1), 77–95.

Millikan SD 2012. Teachers' perceptions of the use of differentiated instruction on student achievement in mathematics. PhD dissertation. Minneapolis, MN: Walden University. Available at <https://www.proquest.com/docview/963536758?fromopenview=true&pq-origsite=gscholar>. Accessed 28 February 2023.

Moon, T. R. (2005). The role of assessment in differentiation. *Theory into Practice*, 44(3), 226–233. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15430421tip4403_7

Muthomi, M., & Mbugua, Z. (2014). Effectiveness of Differentiated Instruction on Secondary School Students Achievement in Mathematics. *International Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, Retrieved January 14, 2018 from http://www.ijastnet.com/journals/Vol_4_No_1_January_2014/12.pdf.

Naimiea, Z., Siraj, S., Piaw, C.Y., Shagholi, R., & Abuzaid, R.A. (2010). Do you think your match is made in heaven? Teaching styles/learning styles match and mismatch revisited. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2, 349–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.03.023>.

National Center for Education Statistics (2023). NAEP Long-term Trend Assessment Results: Reading and Mathematics. Retrieved from: Nation's Report Card.

Nelsen, J. B. (2011). The impact of differentiated instruction on student mathematics achievement in primary schools. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 23(2), 175-183

Pagtulon-an, E. & Tan D. (2018). Students' Mathematics Performance and Self-efficacy Beliefs in a Rich Assessment Tasks Environment. *Asian Academic Research Journal of Multidisciplinary*. 5(2), 54-64.

Peteros, E., Gamboa, A., Etcuban, J. O., Dinauanao, A., Sitoy, R., & Arcadio, R.M. (2020). Factors affecting mathematics performance of junior high school students. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 15(1), 2-13. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/5938>

Prast, H.H., 2023. How do Dutch teachers implement differentiation in primary mathematics. Springer Link.

Purcell, J. H., Burns, D. E., Tomlinson, C. A., Imbeau, M. B. & Martin, J. L. 2002. Bridging the Gap: A Tool and Technique to Analyze and Evaluate Gifted Education Curricular Units. *Gifted child quarterly* 46(4): 306– 321.

Rienties, B., Brouwer, N., & Lygo-Baker, S. (2013). The effects of online professional development on higher education teachers' beliefs and intentions towards learning facilitation and technology. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 29, 122- 131.

Roy, A., Guay, F., & Valois, P. (2013). Teaching to address diverse learning needs: Development and validation of a differentiated instruction scale. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 17(11), 1186-1204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2012.743604>

Santangelo, T., & Tomlinson, C. A. (2012). Teacher educators' perceptions and use of differentiated instruction practices: An exploratory investigation. *Action in Teacher Education*, 34, 309-327. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01626620.2012.717032>

Slavin, R. E. (2003). "Educational Psychology: Theory and Practice" (7th ed.). Boston: Allyn and Bacon).

Smale-Jacobse, A. E., Meijer, A., Helms-Lorenz, M., & Maulana, R. (2019). Differentiated instruction in secondary education: A systematic review of research evidence. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 2366. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02366>

Small M 2017. *Good questions: Great ways to differentiate mathematics instruction in the standards-based classroom* (3rd ed). New York, NY: Teachers College Press.

Smit, R., & Humpert, W. (2012). Differentiated instruction in small schools. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 28(8), 1152-1162.

Smith, T. M., Cobb, P., Farran, D. C., Cordray, D. S., & Munter, C. (2013). Evaluating Math Recovery: Assessing the causal impact of a diagnostic tutoring program on student achievement. *American Educational Research Journal*, 50(2), 397-428. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831212469045>

Suprayogi, M. N., Valcke, M., & Godwin, R. (2017). Teachers and their implementation of differentiated instruction in the classroom. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 67, 291-301.

Tambaoan, S. T., Gaylo, D. N. (2019). Differentiating instruction in a mathematics classroom. Its effects on senior high school learners' academic performance and engagement in basic calculus. Bukidnon State University. *International Journal of English and Education*. ISSN: 2278-4012, volume:8, Issue2.

Tomlinson, C. A., & Imbeau, M. (2010). *Leading and managing a differentiated classroom*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.

Tomlinson CA (2014). *The differentiated classroom: Responding to the needs of all learners* (2nd ed). Alexandria, VA: ASCD.

Tomlinson, C. A. (2017). *How to differentiate instruction in academically diverse classrooms*. ASCD.

Trochim, W. M., & Donnelly, J.P. (2008). *The Research Methods Knowledge Base* (3rd Ed.) Atmic Dog

Unal, Aslihan; Unal, Zafer; and Bodur, Yasar (2022) "Differentiated Instruction and Kindergarten through 5th Grade Teachers," *Georgia Educational Researcher*: Vol. 19: Iss. 2, Article 2. DOI: 10.20429/ger.2022.190202^[1]_[SEP] Available at: <https://digitalcommons.georgiasouthern.edu/gerjournal/vol19/iss2/2>

Valiandes, S., & Neophytou, L. (2017). [Differentiated teaching. Functional and effective implementation]. *Pedio*.

Walker-Dalhouse, D., Risko, V., Esworthy, C., Grasley, E., & Stephan, M. (2010). Crossing boundaries and initiating conversations about RTI: Understanding and applying differentiated classroom instruction. *The Reading Teacher*, 63(1), 84- 87. doi: 10.1598/RT.63.1.9

Warner, R.M.(2013).*Applied"statistics:From bivariate through multivariate techniques*. Thousand Oaks, CA. Sage Publications.

Watts-Taffe, S., Broach, L., Marinak, B., McDonald Connor, C., & Walker-Dalhouse, D. (2012). Differentiated instruction: Making informed teacher decisions. *The Reading Teacher*, 66(4), 303-314.

Way, J., Reece, A., Bobis, J., Anderson, J., & Martin, A. (2015), Improving student motivation and engagement in mathematics through one-to-one interactions. In M. Marshman, V. Geiger, & A. Bennison (Eds.), *Mathematics education in the margins: Proceedings of the 38th annual conference of the Mathematics Education Research Group of Australasia* (pp. 627-634). MERGA.

Wilkinson, C. A. (2013). *Differentiating delivery of instruction with online learning modules for teacher candidates*. (Unpublished PhD dissertation). State University of New York, USA.

Woolfolk, A. (2016). "Educational Psychology" (13th ed.). Pearson)

Yavuz, A. C. (2020). The effects of differentiated instruction on Turkish students' L2 achievement, and student and teacher perceptions. *Eurasian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 6(2), 313-335. doi: <https://doi.org/10.32601/ejal.776002>

B. ELEMENTS

a. Figures and Tables

The figures and tables should have a numbered explanatory label posted below the graphic element. Each figure and table should have a descriptive caption that describes and defines all the abbreviations included. If the element contains data from external sources, an explanatory citation should be included. Photographic images can be submitted if they are saved in JPEG format at a resolution of 300 dpi. The tables are required to have, if appropriate or possible, the width and the height of the size of an entire page avoiding the splitting on more pages.

b. Formulas and Equations

The formulas and equation could be inserted as objects if created with another external program (Wolfram Mathematica, Matlab, etc) or by using Microsoft Equation Editor included on the last editions of Microsoft Office.

c. Lists

Any kind of list can be part of the article. Numbers, letters, roman numbers, bullets, etc. can be used as their components.

d. Supplementary Files

Appendixes, supplementary files or any other resource related to the research could be attached at original manuscript. The attachments will be placed on the "Supplementary files" section on right side of the screen. It is highly recommended, for a better and faster publication process, that all the files to be submitted together and in their final and definitive form.

C. LIMITATIONS

There is absolutely **no limit** and **no extra charges** on:

- how many pages are allowed for a research paper. It depends on many factors, the researcher should decide that. A 5-25 pages research article it is only a recommendation, not a limit.
- how many authors a research paper may have. Collaboration is the key.
- how many graphic elements, figures, pictures, photos, tables, appendixes a research paper may contain. We are strongly encouraging our authors on providing any possible method designated to ensure better and faster information exchange.

D. MANUSCRIPT FILE FORMAT

A Microsoft Word, any version (2003, 2010), file or any other document editor is recommended. External files as PowerPoint presentation, image files (*.jpg, *.bmp, *.png), Excel tables, AutoCAD files, can be included.

E. LANGUAGES ACCEPTED

Article written on English, Spanish, Portuguese, Italian and French are accepted. They can contain abstracts\titles on English too. Articles written in two columns (English + another language) are accepted.

Leandy B. Milallos, Maedel Joy V. Escote
DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: A QUASI-EXPERIMENTAL
STUDY
